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UDC 331.108.37

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Formation of personnel security system at agritourism enterprises

Relevance of the research topic. *The study of the issue of the formation of a personnel security system at agritourism enterprises is conditioned by the significant influence of the changing external environment on these processes.*

Formulation of the problem. *Personnel security is based on the interaction of managers and personnel of the enterprise, therefore, the effectiveness of their activities depends on an effective motivational mechanism, individualization and non-discrimination in remuneration, guarantee of timely and full payment of wages. Therefore, when forming a system for assessing the level of personnel security of agritourism enterprises, it is necessary to take into account these factors, eliminating personnel risks, which determines the relevance of the research topic.*

Setting the purpose and objectives of the study – *to investigate the formation of the personnel security system at agritourism enterprises.*

Research method or methodology. *The article uses the following methods: abstract-logical, monographic, graphic, analysis and synthesis, systematization.*

Presentation of the main material (research results). *Summarizing the demonstrated methods of personnel safety assessment, we systematize actions to neutralize and prevent risks to personnel safety of agritourism enterprises: prevention of theft, damage to property and destructive actions by*

the personnel of the enterprise; prevention of damage to equipment, leakage of commercial information, cybercrime, appropriation of company assets; prevention of the negative impact on the economic security of insufficiently qualified employees of the enterprise, ineffective personnel management regarding the preservation and development of the intellectual potential of the enterprise, etc.

Field of application of results. *The results of the study can be used in practical activities for the implementation of the personnel security system at agritourism enterprises.*

Conclusions on the article. *Taking into account the results of the conducted research, it is possible to consider the system of evaluating personnel security of agritourism enterprises according to the following blocks of indicators to be relevant: indicators of social and motivational personnel security; indicators of staff availability and efficiency of their use; indicators of personnel safety; indicators of professional personnel security; indicators of anti-conflict personnel security; indicators of assessment of personnel security system. These indicators satisfy the information needs of various interest groups of agritourism enterprises, that is, they have a stakeholder-oriented approach of synergistic hysteresis, taking into account the temporal factor.*

Keywords: *management, system, personnel security, enterprise, agritourism.*

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Формування системи кадрової безпеки на підприємствах агротуризму

Актуальність теми дослідження. *Дослідження питання формування системи кадрової безпеки на підприємствах агротуризму обумовлюється значним впливом мінливого зовнішнього середовища на дані процеси.*

Постановка проблеми. *Кадрова безпека ґрунтується на взаємодії керівників та персоналу підприємства, тому ефективність їх діяльності залежить від ефективного мотиваційного механізму, індивідуалізації та відсутності дискримінації в оплаті праці, гарантії своєчасної та повної виплати заробітної плати. Тож при формуванні системи оцінки рівня кадрової безпеки підприємств агротуризму треба обов'язково враховувати дані фактори, елімінуючи кадрові ризики, що обумовлює актуальність теми дослідження.*

Постановка мети і завдань дослідження – дослідити формування системи кадрової безпеки на підприємствах агротуризму.

Метод або методологія дослідження. *В статті використано наступні методи: абстрактно-логічний, монографічний, графічний, аналізу і синтезу, систематизації.*

Презентація основного матеріалу (результати дослідження). *Узагальнюючи продемонстровані методики оцінки кадрової безпеки, систематизуємо дії з нейтралізації та попередження ризиків кадровій безпеці підприємств агротуризму: запобігання крадіжок, псування майна та деструктивних дій із боку персоналу підприємства, запобігання псуванню техніки, витоку комерційної інформації, кіберзлочинності, привласненні активів підприємства, запобігання негативного впливу на економічну безпеку недостатньо кваліфікованих працівників підприємства, неефективного управління персоналом щодо збереження та розвитку інтелектуального потенціалу підприємства тощо.*

Галузь застосування результатів. *Результати дослідження можуть бути використані в практичній діяльності для реалізації системи кадрової безпеки на підприємствах агротуризму.*

Висновки за статтю. *Зважаючи на результати проведеного дослідження, можна вважати актуальною систему оцінки кадрової безпеки підприємств агротуризму за наступними блоками показників: показники соціально-мотиваційної кадрової безпеки; показники забезпеченості кадрами та ефективності їх використання; показники безпеки життєдіяльності персоналу; показники професійної кадрової безпеки; показники антиконфліктної кадрової безпеки; показники оцінки системи кадрової безпеки. Дані показники задовільняють інформаційні потреби різних груп інтересів підприємств агротуризму, тобто мають стейкхолдерорієнтований підхід синергетичного гістерезису з урахуванням темпорального чиннику.*

Ключові слова: *менеджмент, система, кадрова безпека, підприємство, агротуризм.*

Formulation of the problem. Personnel security is based on the interaction of managers and personnel of the enterprise, therefore, the effectiveness of their activities depends on an effective motivational mechanism, individualization and non-discrimination in remuneration, guarantee of timely and full payment of wages. Therefore, when forming a system for assessing the level of personnel security of agritourism enterprises, it is necessary to take into account these factors, eliminating personnel risks, which determines the relevance of the research topic.

Analysis of recent research and publications. The state of protection of personnel security is determined mainly by two groups of indicators: indicators of personnel composition and realization of personnel potential, as well as indicators of risks and threats to personnel security [7; 9]. In the process of synthesizing the integral indicator of personnel security at agritourism enterprises, an analytical method can be used, which is based on the selection of a set of coefficients, the determination of their limit values and weights, and the calculation of group indicators. This makes it possible to obtain a generalized integral indicator, the value of which corresponds to one of 4 levels of security: high, medium, minimal or critical [3; 8]. It is for this reason that indicators of personnel security include the coefficients of harmony and timeliness of salary payments, the ratio of growth rates of productivity and wages, financial losses due to the fault of employees and physical aging of personnel, as well as groups of indicators of social security of employees and safe working conditions. Thus, the integrated assessment based on the research of various scientific schools includes 6 groups of indicators: staff stability and loyalty, characteristics of the remuneration system, the educational and intellectual level of employees, the effectiveness of the use of personnel, social security of personnel and safe working conditions [1–10], the practical side the application of which should be investigated more systematically.

The formulation of the goals of the article is to investigate the formation of the personnel security system at agritourism enterprises.

Presenting main material. Taking into account the modern model of human economic behavior, the homo-economicus, it is possible to clearly define the main functions that the economic security service should perform, provided it is present at the agro-

tourism enterprise: protection of production activity of the enterprise and protection of commercial information from unauthorized access; implementation of special information systems to counter the acquisition of commercial secrets; identification and neutralization of possible channels of leakage of confidential information in the process of production activity; ensuring the protection of premises, equipment, products, personnel of the enterprise against illegal actions of competitors.

Such a department should include an economist, a lawyer, a risk manager, a technologist, a marketer, a programmer, and other specialists based on the specifics of the functioning of an agribusiness enterprise [6], whose task should be, among other things, the signature diagnosis of the characteristics-pathologies of the external and internal environment, which can be demonstrated by the monitoring matrix of actual personnel security factors in the management system of agritourism enterprises (Table 1). With regard to the factors indicated in the presented matrix, for the formation of a methodology for assessing the level of personnel security of agritourism enterprises, the national labor mentality is very important, which generally reflects the level of labor consciousness of society and its social groups regarding the perception of the meaning of labor activity and reflects the needs, interests, value orientations of the population, which determine the motivational motives of work behavior in the labor market [4]. This mentality is creative, not neutral or destructive. That is, the task of personnel security subjects at the enterprise is facilitated in this regard and consists in preventing objects from falling into institutional traps.

The second factor is the business philosophy that has developed in Ukraine since independence. One of its characteristic manifestations is the focus on the active use of methods of unfair competition in all spheres of economic activity [3]. However, with the growth of national consciousness and decentralization, this factor is gradually leveling off.

The third factor is the shortcomings of the current labor legislation regarding personnel and the quality of working life, which in the first place pushes rural residents to labor migration.

The fourth factor is the mining of physical objects, which is a consequence of the war and directly affects social and labor relations, and, accordingly, personnel safety.

Table 1. Monitoring matrix of actual personnel security factors in the management system of agritourism enterprises

Objective	Subjective
Specific labor mentality of the population	Antisocial orientations of business owners
Orientation of domestic entrepreneurs to the active use of methods of unfair competition	Inefficiency of the personnel management system
Disadvantages of the current legislation	Inefficiency of staff motivation
Substitutability of physical objects	Non-compliance of remuneration with the criteria of dignity
High risk of physical destruction and seizure of property by occupying forces	Insufficient professional training of enterprise managers, including safety training
High risk of stopping production due to problems of an epidemiological nature	Insufficient professional training of heads of structural divisions, including safety training

Regarding the high risk of physical destruction and seizure of property by the occupying forces, we have direct influence in the areas of military (combat) operations or those areas under temporary occupation.

In addition, there is a high risk of stopping production due to problems of an epidemiological nature.

The action of subjective factors directly depends on the owners of enterprises or the management bodies authorized by them.

The first subjective factor is the antisocial orientation of the owners, usually consisting in ignoring the principles of social responsibility not only to society, but also to the staff, which is expressed in:

- positioning of personnel as one of the types of resources necessary for conducting statutory activities, and not as human capital, the development of which requires constant targeted investments, economic, social and psychological support;
- striving to minimize costs related to personnel activities, including by saving costs for training employees, forming a corporate spirit and corporate culture in the workforce;
- selection of top management focused on a totalitarian style of management and ignoring the requirements of the doctrine of human capital development, etc. [6].

The second subjective factor is the ineffectiveness of the personnel management system, which does not contribute to ensuring the competitiveness of agritourism enterprises, increasing the efficiency of their activities [4; 8].

Taking into account the factors presented in the matrix and focusing on the research of the methodological principles of determining the level of compliance of the staff of agritourism enterprises with the task of implementing development programs, implementing production-technological and commercial innovations, creating prerequi-

sites for eliminating personnel risks, with the subsequent establishment on this basis of the integral indicator of compliance with personnel safety of the enterprise [9], we need to critically analyze already tested methods. Thus, the level of profitability of ensuring personnel security, which is mainly influenced by the following indicators: the share of personnel who were hired, but resigned at their own will during the trial period, the specific weight of the costs of training and development of personnel, and the specific weight of the premium and bonus parts of the salary pay The parameters of the specific weight of personnel training costs and premium and bonus parts of wages have the greatest impact on the level of profitability of ensuring personnel security, therefore, personnel development through training and improvement of the motivational mechanism of enterprises can be considered as key components of the mechanism of ensuring personnel security of agritourism enterprises [7].

Personnel security in the management system of agritourism enterprises should be based on a number of indicators formed on the basis of the elimination of personnel risks:

- labor force mobility (employee movement indexes; employee admission and exit level indexes; employee dismissal indexes for reasons; workforce supply and demand indexes);
- use of labor force (indices of the use of working time of employees; indices of the number of workers who were in conditions of forced part-time employment; indices of the level of forced part-time employment; indices of loss of working time due to being in conditions of forced part-time employment);
- wage level (indexes of the average monthly nominal wage; indices of the average monthly real wage; indices of the average monthly wage of full-time employees; indices of the number of employ-

ees whose wages are paid within the subsistence minimum; specific weight of the structural components of the wage fund; indices of the average monthly wage for hours worked);

- the state of wage payments (indices of arrears to the population from the payment of wages and social benefits; indices of arrears from the payment of wages; the ratio of the amount of arrears from the payment of wages to the wage fund; indices of arrears from the payment of wages to employees of economically active enterprises at the expense of budget funds);

- the state of registered collective agreements, labor disputes and strikes (indices of the number of registered collective agreements; indices of the number of employees covered by collective agreements; indices of the number of collective labor disputes) [8].

In addition to the factors that form personnel security (professional, informational, social-motivational security, life security, interpersonal security), in the period of crises and bifurcations, the personal level of responsibility is especially important (professional and personal competences, individual work performance, employee labor competitiveness, personal labor responsibility employee, rights and obligations of the employee) [9]. Therefore, in order to obtain an objective assessment of the level of personnel security of the enterprise, it is advisable to monitor a large number of indicators that comprehensively analyze the state of the agritourism enterprise in order to fully take into account the systemic nature of its personnel security [4].

Thus, taking into account the need for the complementary influence of formal and informal institutions, it is possible to evaluate the economic security of the enterprise by its components: intellectual – various indicators of personnel turnover, the level of R&D, personnel education, etc.; personnel – similar to the previous one, their combination is possible [2]. The main groups of criteria directly in personnel security are indicators of: the numerical composition of the personnel and its dynamics; qualifications and intellectual potential; efficiency of personnel use; qualities of the motivational system [9].

Explicit negative actions regarding the interests of objects of economic security, which require preventive fixing in the relevant indicators to avoid institutional traps and prevent opportunistic behavior, are as follows: deviation of the values of the established control indicators from the limit in the

negative direction; an increase in the amplitude of the dynamics of the established indicators by values greater than permissible; occurrence of unexplained financial, technological and informational phenomena and processes; occurrence of force majeure circumstances; unclear or negative behavior of individual employees and their groups; the occurrence of conflict situations between internal and external business entities; suspicious interest on the part of external subjects in the activities of the company, division, object, its personnel, management, information, material means and funds; facts of embezzlement, damage to property, disappearance of money and documents, other illegal actions; attempts of unauthorized access and use of internal information; the emergence of problems of personal safety of employees, etc. [10].

Regarding the method of determining the integral indicator of personnel security of an agritourism enterprise, social indicators of economic security should be used: the level of remuneration in relation to the average indicator for the industry or the economy as a whole, the level of salary arrears, loss of working time, the structure of personnel potential [6]. Disturbing the specified set of indicators, in the general list of indicators for monitoring and evaluating the security system, among internal threats, it is possible to single out: outdated methods and forms of communication, distortion of information; non-compliance with production standards, non-compliance with technological requirements and quality standards; injury, damage; conflicts, non-fulfillment of agreements, unauthorized leakage of information; misuse of funds, violations of the regulator's requirements, conscious (falsification of documents) and unconscious (errors) [7].

Specifically, regarding indicators of personnel and intellectual security (the author combines personnel and intellectual security in his research, considering them inseparable due to the modern features of the development of the knowledge economy): labor productivity; personnel turnover ratio; salary return ratio; coefficient of educational level; the share of costs for internal (external) research work in the total costs of production; coefficient of the share of costs for personnel management [2].

The approach in which the subsystems of indicators of personnel security in the context of the stages of personnel management at an agritourism enterprise are identified is sufficiently justified, namely:

indicators of the level of personnel security in the process of recruitment and adaptation of personnel (complexity of the use of assessment technologies in the process of personnel recruitment, the proportion of personnel who were hired but did not complete the probationary period due to inadequacy of the qualifications for the position or for other reasons, the proportion of personnel who were hired but voluntarily resigned during the probationary period, the proportion of personnel who were hired but violated labor discipline during the trial period, the specific weight of the costs of attracting personnel in the total amount of costs for ensuring personnel security); indicators of the level of ensuring personnel security in the process of personnel development and control (the share of personnel who did not pass certification, the share of personnel who underwent training and development programs, the share of personnel who underwent career development at the enterprise, the share of personnel who created a threat to personnel security enterprises due to violations or abuses, the specific weight of costs for training and development of personnel in the total amount of costs for ensuring personnel security); indicators of the level of ensuring personnel security in the process of motivating and forming personnel loyalty (the share of personnel who resigned or were fired for any reason, the level of personnel satisfaction, the level of personnel loyalty, the level of personnel involvement, the specific weight of the premium and bonus parts in the structure of the wage fund) [10].

Summarizing the set of indicators for assessing the personnel security of an agritourism enterprise allows the selection of its components:

1) life safety: the level of workplace organization; coefficient of labor discipline; share of labor protection costs in total personnel costs; injury frequency rate; the share of workers employed in conditions that do not meet sanitary and hygienic standards; the growth rate of the occupational morbidity rate of the staff; the ratio of the actual working time fund of one employee and the maximum possible; loss of working time due to illness;

2) social and motivational: specific weight of wages in the cost of production; the growth rate of the average monthly wage; the ratio of the average salary level to the average level in the industry; the ratio of growth rates of the wage fund and profit; the share of additional salary in the basic salary; the

share of employees who receive a pension; productivity; the ratio of growth rates of labor productivity and wages; staff turnover rate; salary capacity; the share of expenses for cultural and household services of employees in the total expenses for personnel; the rate of growth of the housing and communal services development coefficient; the share of deductions for social activities in the total amount of personnel costs; level of social security of employees; the share of part-time employees; the share of freelancers and part-time employees;

3) professional: coefficient of educational level of employees; the share of employees trained in new professions at the enterprise; the share of personnel employed in NDDKP; the share of costs for education and professional development; invention coefficient; coefficient of personnel development; profitability of personnel costs; the share of employees who have undergone professional training or improved their qualifications; an increase in the cost of education per employee; staffing ratio;

4) anti-conflict security: level of organizational culture development; level of staff loyalty; the level of conflict in the enterprise; degree of employee satisfaction with work; the level of social tension at the enterprise; the level of cohesion of the labor team; the degree of employee satisfaction with the leadership style; share of registered conflicts [8; 10].

The author argues these conclusions with a systematic analysis and generalization of the components of personnel security, among which he singles out in particular: health security; physical security; technological security; career security; financial security; administratively independent security; aesthetic safety; intellectual security; pension and insurance security; patriotic security; anti-conflict security; psychological and communication security [9].

6 levels of security can be distinguished: owners, shareholders; top management, leadership; personnel; organization of business processes; operational activity of the enterprise; accounting, analysis, audit [2].

This division provides the basis for the formation of separate indicators that would eliminate personnel risks by modes and attributes through the appropriate basis of value and in accordance with the signature of impulses for each level. For example, to ensure a high level of personnel security of agritourism enterprises, the following parameters are necessary: staff stability, their education-

al and qualification level, labor discipline and social protection [3]. And to assess the risk, for example, of abuse of office, it is advisable to use the following indicators: openness, embezzlement, organizational tolerance, corporate norms [10].

Summarizing the demonstrated methods of personnel safety assessment, we systematize actions to neutralize and prevent risks to personnel safety of agritourism enterprises: prevention of theft, damage to property and destructive actions by the personnel of the enterprise; prevention of damage to equipment, leakage of commercial information, cybercrime, appropriation of company assets; prevention of the negative impact on the economic security of insufficiently qualified employees of the enterprise, ineffective personnel management regarding the preservation and development of the intellectual potential of the enterprise; prevention of risks and threats related to personnel, their intellectual potential and labor relations in general; prevention of official abuse and fraud by employees (unauthorized access, attempts to hack the network, sale of information to competitors, etc.), kidnapping and blackmail of key specialists; prevention of theft of financial and material and technical means, destruction of property and valuables, disclosure, loss, leakage, distortion/destruction of official information, malfunction of technical means; provision of production activities, including means of informatization, etc.

Conclusions.

Taking into account the results of the conducted research, it is possible to consider the system of evaluating personnel security of agritourism enterprises according to the following blocks of indicators to be relevant: indicators of social and motivational personnel security; indicators of staff availability and efficiency of their use; indicators of personnel safety; indicators of professional personnel security; indicators of anti-conflict personnel security; indicators of assessment of personnel security system. These indicators satisfy the information needs of various interest groups of agritourism enterprises, that is, they have a stakeholder-oriented approach of synergistic hysteresis, determine the main drivers, modes and attributes of personnel security, allow to orientate on the risk hedging policy, forming an implicit and explicit field of personnel threats in the turbulent period of crises and bifurcations, and also to choose adequate tools for adaptation to the internal and external

environment in the field of influence of opportunistic phenomena based on the signature of impulses of problems, anomalies and collisions and to identify manifestations of hysteresis of the management system of agritourism enterprises taking into account the temporal factor.

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